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Research Article

**THE ANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND
VALIDATION FOR THE SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF
SETRALINE & ALPRAZOLAM BY USING RP- HPLC**O. Swathi^{1*}, Chaitanya Bangari², S.Bhayalata³, Dr.M.B.VenkatapathiRaju⁴¹Avanathi Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Vizianagaram, AP-531162.**Abstract:**

High performance liquid chromatography is at present one of the most sophisticated tool of the analysis. The estimation of Sertaline Hcl and Alprazolam was done by RP-HPLC. The Phosphate buffer was p^H 2.8 and the mobile phase was optimized with consists of Methanol: Phosphate buffer mixed in the ratio of 55:45 % v/ v. A C_{18} column C_{18} (4.6 x 150mm, 5 μ m, Make: XTerra) or equivalent chemically bonded to porous silica particles was used as stationary phase. The detection was carried out using UV detector at 225 nm. The solutions were chromatographed at a constant flow rate of 1.0 ml/min. the linearity range of Sertaline Hcl and Alprazolam were found to be from 100-500 μ g/ml.of Sertaline Hcl and 1-5 μ g/ml of Alprazolam. Linear regression coefficient was not more than 0.999.

The values of % RSD are less than 2% indicating accuracy and precision of the method. The percentage recovery varies from 98-102% of Sertaline Hcl and Alprazolam. LOD and LOQ were found to be within limit.

The results obtained on the validation parameters met ICH and USP requirements .it inferred the method found to be simple, accurate, precise and linear. The method was found to be having suitable application in routine laboratory analysis with high degree of accuracy and precision.

Key words: Sertaline ,Alprazolam, accuracy ,precision and linearity.

Corresponding author:**O. Swathi,**

Avanathi Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Vizianagaram, AP-531162.

Swathi.ommi1997@gmail.com / pharmamadhuphd@gmail.com

9121726149 / 7799263656.

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

The analysis of Sertaline & Alprazolam by simultaneous estimation by RP-HPLC. Spectrophotometer, HPLC and HPTLC are the reported analytical methods for compounds either individually or in combination with other dosage form. Hence, it was felt that, there is a need of new analytical method development for the simultaneous estimation of Sertaline & Alprazolam in pharmaceutical dosage form[1].

Present work is aimed to develop a new, simple, fast, rapid, accurate, efficient and reproducible RP-HPLC

method for the simultaneous analysis of Sertaline & Alprazolam. The developed method will be validated conferring to ICH guidelines [2]

The Objective of the present work was to study the simultaneous estimation of Sertaline & Alprazolam by RP-HPLC method by optimizing the chromatographic conditions and to developed method is validated conferring to ICH guidelines for various parameters specified in ICH guidelines, Q2 (R1).

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY:**Instruments used**

SL.No	Instrument	Model
1	HPLC	WATERS, software: Empower, 2695 sepapropionn module,PDA detector.
2	UV/VWAS spectrophotometer	LABINDIA UV 3000 ⁺
3	pH meter	Adwa – AD 1020
4	Weighing machine	Afcoset ER-200A
5	Pipettes and Burettes	Borosil
6	Beakers	Borosil

Chemicals used

SL.No	Chemical	Brand
1	Sertaline HCL	Dr. Reddy`s
2	Alprazolam	Dr. Reddy`s
3	KH ₂ PO ₄	FINER chemical LTD
4	Water and Methanol for HPLC	LICHROSOLV (MERCK)
5	Acetonitrile for HPLC	MOLYCHEM
6	Ortho phosphoric Acid	MERCK

Standard Solution Preparation: [4-10]

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Sertraline and Alprazolam 10mg of working standard into a 10mL & 100ml clean dry volumetric flask add about 7mL of Diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent.

(Stock solution)

Further pipette 3ml & 0.3ml of the above stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluent.

Sample Solution Preparation:

Accurately weigh 10 tablets crush in mortar and pestle and transfer equivalent to 10 mg of Sertraline and Alprazolam (marketed formulation) sample into a 10mL clean dry volumetric flask add about 7mL of Diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent.

Assay calculation

$$\text{Assay \%} = \frac{\text{sample area}}{\text{Standard area}} \times \frac{\text{dilution sample}}{\text{dilution of standard}} \times \frac{P}{100} \times \frac{\text{Avg. wt}}{Lc} \times 100$$

Where:

Avg. wt = average weight of tablets

P = Percentage purity of working standard

LC = Label Claim of Povidone mg/ml.

Chromatographic trials for simultaneous estimation of Povidone and Ornidazole by RP- HPLC

	Trail -1	Trail 2	Trail 3	Trail 4	Trail 5 optimised method
Mobile phase	Water: Methanol(50:50%v/v)	Phosphate buffer(0.05M)pH 4.0:Methanol(40:60%v/v)	Phosphate buffer (0.05M)pH 4.0:Methanol(4 0:60%v/v)	Phosphate buffer (0.05M)pH 3.6:ACN(40: 60%v/v)	40% buffer 60% acetonitrile Ph3.6
Diluent	Mobile phase was used as the diluent	Mobile phase was used as the diluents	Mobile phase was used as the diluents	Mobile phase was used as the diluent	Mobile phase was used as the diluent
Flow rate	1ml/min	1.0ml per min	0.8 ml per min	0.8 ml per min	1.0 ml per min
Column	Make; Xterra C18 (4.6*250mm) 5µm	Make; Xterra C18 (4.6*250mm) 5µm	Symmetry C18 5µm (4.6*250mm) Make; waters	Symmetry C18 5µm (4.6*250mm) Make; waters	Symmetry C18 (4.6 x 250mm, 5µm, Make: Waters)
Detector wavelength	225 nm	225 nm	225 nm	225nm	225nm
Column oven	Ambient	Ambient	Ambient	Ambient	Ambient
Injection volume	10µl	10µl	10µl	20µl	10µl
Running time	5min	2 min	10 min	8min	5min

(Stock solution)

Further pipette 3 ml of Sertaline and Alprazolam of the above stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluent.

Technique:

Inject 20 µL of the standard, sample into the chromatographic system and measure the areas for Sertraline and Alprazolam peaks and calculate the %Assay by utilization the formulae

System suitability

- Tailing factor for the peaks due to Povidone and Ornidazole in standard solution should not be more than 1.5.
- Theoretical plates for the Povidone and Ornidazole peaks in standard solution should not be less than 2000.

Validation parameters such as specificity, Linearity, Range, Accuracy, Precision, Repeatability, Intermediate Precision, Detection Limit, Quantitation Limit, Robustness also studied [5-10].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

OPTIMIZED CHROMATOGRAM IS OBTAINED BY FOLLOWING CONDITIONS:

Trial 1:

Trial chromatogram for Sertraline HCL and Alprazolam

From the above chromatogram it was observed that the Sertraline HCL peak was splitted

Trial 2:

Trial chromatogram for Sertraline HCL and Alprazolam

From the above chromatogram it was observed that the Sertraline HCL and Alprazolam peaks are splitted

Trial 3:

Trial chromatogram for Sertraline HCL and Alprazolam

From the above chromatogram it was observed that the Sertraline HCL and Alprazolam peaks are splitted

Trial 4:**Trial chromatogram for Sertraline HCL and Alprazolam**

From the above chromatogram it was observed that the Sertraline HCL and Alprazolam peaks are splitted

Trial 5:**Trial chromatogram for Sertraline HCL and Alprazolam**

From the above chromatogram it was observed that the Sertraline HCL and Alprazolam peaks are splitted.

Chromatogram for Sertraline HCL and Alprazolam**chromatogram for blank**

From the above chromatogram it was observed that there are no interferences.

Chromatogram for Sertraline HCL and Alprazolam sample Preparation

From the above chromatogram it was observed that the sertraline and alprazolam peaks are well separated

Retention time of Sertraline HCL – 2.342min

Retention time of Alprazolam - 3.282 min.

Chromatogram for Sertraline HCL and Alprazolam Standard Preparation

Retention time of Sertraline HCL – 2.344 min

Retention time of Alprazolam - 3.286 min.

SYSTEM SUITABILITY:

chromatogram for system suitability
Calculation: (For Sertraline)

$$\text{Assay \%} = \frac{\text{AT}}{\text{AS}} \times \frac{\text{WS}}{\text{DS}} \times \frac{\text{DT}}{\text{WT}} \times \frac{\text{P}}{100} \times \frac{\text{Avg. Wt}}{\text{Label Claim}} \times 100$$

Where: AT = average area counts of sample preparation.

As= average area counts of standard preparation.

WS = Weight of working standard taken in mg.

P = Percentage purity of working standard

LC = LABEL CLAIM OF Sertraline mg/ml.

System Suitability Results:

- 1). Tailing factor Obtained from the standard injection is 1.3
- 2). Theoretical Plates Obtained from the standard injection is 4668.7

Assay Results:

Weight of 10 tablets: 1.25 grams

Average Weight : 0.125grams

$$= \frac{1314011}{1311967} \times \frac{10}{10} \times \frac{3}{10} \times \frac{10}{25} \times \frac{10}{3} \times \frac{99.8}{100} \times \frac{125}{50} \times 100 = 99.95\%$$

Calculation: (For Alprazolam)

$$\text{Assay \%} = \frac{\text{AT}}{\text{AS}} \times \frac{\text{WS}}{\text{DS}} \times \frac{\text{DT}}{\text{WT}} \times \frac{\text{P}}{100} \times \frac{\text{Avg. Wt.}}{\text{Label Claim}} \times 100$$

Where:

AT = average area counts of sample preparation.

As= average area counts of standard preparation.

WS = Weight of working standard taken in mg.

P = Percentage purity of working standard

LC = LABEL CLAIM OF Alprazolam mg/ml.

System Suitability Results:

- 1). Tailing factor Obtained from the standard injection is 1.3
- 2). Theoretical Plates Obtained from the standard injection is 6090.3

Assay Results:

Weight of 10 tablets: 1.25 grams

Average Weight : 0.125grams

$$= \frac{125260}{124581} \times \frac{10}{100} \times \frac{0.3}{10} \times \frac{10}{25} \times \frac{10}{3} \times \frac{99.7}{100} \times \frac{125}{0.5} \times 100 = 100.24\%$$

Results of system suitability parameters for Sertraline and Alprazolam

S.No	Name	Retention time(min)	Area (µV sec)	Height (µV)	USP resolution	USP tailing	USP plate count
1	Sertraline	2.3	124505	213642		1.2	4673.4
2	Alprazolam	3.2	1308495	154566	6 0	1.3	6090.3

Acceptance criteria:

- Resolution between two drugs must be not less than 2
- Theoretical plates must be not less than 2000
- Tailing factor must be not less than 0.9 and not more than 2.
- It was found from above data that all the system suitability parameters for developed method were within the limit.

VALIDATION PARAMETERS:**PRECISION:**

Precision of the method was carried out for standard solutions as described under experimental work. The corresponding chromatograms and results are shown below.

chromatogram for standard injection -1

chromatogram for standard injection-2

chromatogram for standard injection-3

chromatogram for standard injection-4

chromatogram for standard injection-5

Results of method precession for Sertraline HCL:

Injection	Area
Injection-1	1302729
Injection-2	1302947
Injection-3	1303236
Injection-4	1303977
Injection-5	1309759
Average	1304529.8
Standard Deviation	2961.1
%RSD	0.2

Results of method precession for Alprazolam:

Injection	Area
Injection-1	123149
Injection-2	123766
Injection-3	124271
Injection-4	124691
Injection-5	124956
Average	124162.7
Standard Deviation	725.6
%RSD	0.6

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD for sample should be NMT 2
- The %RSD for the standard solution is below 1, which is within the limits hence method is precise.

INTERMEDIATE PRECESSION (RUGGEDNESS):

There was no significant change in assay content and system suitability parameters at different conditions of ruggedness like day to day and system to system variation.

chromatogram for sample injection-2

chromatogram for sample injection-3

chromatogram for sample injection-4

chromatogram for sample injection-5

Results of Intermediate precision for Sertraline HCL

Injection	Area
Injection-1	1300148
Injection-2	1304520
Injection-3	1305937
Injection-4	1306476
Injection-5	130871
Average	1305070.2
Standard Deviation	3061.8
%RSD	0.2

Results of Intermediate precision for Alprazolam

Injection	Area
Injection-1	122487
Injection-2	122626
Injection-3	122632
Injection-4	122702
Injection-5	122962
Average	122681.8
Standard Deviation	174.8
%RSD	0.1

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD of five different sample solutions should not more than 2
- The %RSD obtained is within the limit, hence the method is rugged.

ACCURACY:

Sample solutions at different concentrations (50%, 100%, and 150%) were prepared and the % recovery was calculated.

Chromatograms For Sample Concentration-50%:**(b) chromatogram for sample concentration-50%**

chromatogram for sample concentration-50%
Chromatograms For Sample Concentration-100%:

(a) chromatogram for sample concentration-100%

(b) chromatogram for sample concentration-100%

(c) chromatogram for sample concentration-100%

Chromatograms For Sample Concentration-150%:**(c) chromatogram for sample concentration-150%****Accuracy (recovery) data for Sertraline HCL**

%Concentration (at specification Level)	Area	Amount Added (mg)	Amount Found (mg)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	656659.5	5.0	5.036	100.7%	99.84%
100%	1304258	10.0	10.003	100.0%	
150%	1854608	14.4	14.224	98.780%	

Accuracy (recovery) data for Alprazolam

%Concentration (at Level)	Area	Amount Added (mg)	Amount Found (mg)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	65800	5.3	5.34	100.8%	100.51%
100%	124353	10	10.10	100.01%	
150%	177940	14.2	14.45	99.68%	

Acceptance Criteria:

- The % Recovery for each level should be between 98.0 to 102.0%.
- The percentage recovery was found to be within the limit (97-103%).

The results obtained for recovery at 50%, 100%, 150% are within the limits. Hence method is accurate

LINEARITY:

The linearity range was found to lie from 100µg/ml to 500µg/ml of sertraline HCL, 5µg/ml to 25µg/ml Of Alprazolam and chromatograms are shown below.

(a) chromatogram for linearity concentration-100µg/ml of Sertaline HCL & 5 µg/ml of Alprazolam

(b) chromatogram for linearity concentration-200 µg/ml of Sertraline HCL & 10 µg/ml of Alprazolam

(c) chromatogram for linearity concentration--300 µg/ml of Sertraline HCL & 15 µg/ml of Alprazolam

(d) chromatogram for linearity concentration-400ppm of Sertraline HCL & 20ppm of Alprazolam

(e) chromatogram for linearity concentration-500 µg/ml of Sertraline HCL & 25 µg/ml of Alprazolam
Area of different concentration of Sertraline HCL

S.No.	Linearity Level	Concentration	Area
1	I	100ppm	668934
2	II	200ppm	956781
3	III	300ppm	1313873
4	IV	400ppm	1563458
5	V	500ppm	1867084
Correlation Coefficient			0.999

Area of different concentration of Alprazolam

S.No	Linearity Level	Concentration	Area
1	I	1ppm	66510
2	II	2ppm	94701
3	III	3ppm	124802
4	IV	4ppm	152731
5	V	5ppm	179732
Correlation Coefficient			0.999

(f) calibration graph for sertraline HCL at 225 nm

calibration graph for alprazolam at 225 nm

Analytical performance parameters of sertraline and alprazolam

Parameters	sertraline	alprazolam
Slope (m)	66574	12529
Intercept (c)	53592	50245
Correlation coefficient (R^2)	0.999	0.999

Acceptance criteria:

Correlation coefficient (R^2) should not be less than 0.999

- The correlation coefficient obtained was 0.999 which is in the acceptance limit. The linearity was established in the range of 10% to 50% of Sertraline HCL and 5% to 25% of Alprazolam.

LIMIT OF DETECTION FOR SERTRALINE HCL AND ALPRAZOLAM

The lowest concentration of the sample was prepared with respect to the base line noise and measured the signal to noise ratio

chromatogram of Sertraline HCL & Alprazolam showing LOD

Results of LOD

Drug name	Baseline noise(μV)	Signal obtained (μV)	S/N ratio
Sertraline HCL	52	152	2.9
Alprazolam	52	156	3

- Signal to noise ratio shall be 3 for LOD solution
- The result obtained is within the limit.

LIMIT OF QUANTIFICATION (LOQ):

The lowest concentration of the sample was prepared with respect to the base line noise and measured the signal to noise ratio.

chromatogram of Sertraline HCL & Alprazolam showing LOQ

Drug name	Baseline noise(μV)	Signal obtained (μV)	S/N ratio
Sertraline HCL	52	522	10.03
Alprazolam	52	524	10.1

- Signal to noise ratio shall be 10 for LOQ solution
- The result obtained is within the limit.

ROBUSTNESS:

The standard and samples of dutasteride and tamsulosin were injected by changing the conditions of chromatography. There was no significant change in the parameters like resolution, tailing factor, asymmetric factor, and plate count.

Variation In Flow

chromatogram showing less flow of 0.8ml/min

chromatogram showing more flow of 1.2ml/min

Flow Rate (ml/min) data for Sertraline HCL

S. No	Flow Rate (ml/min)	System Suitability Results	
		USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	0.8	5339.9	1.4
2	1.0	4673.4	1.3
3	1.2	5216.0	1.4

Flow rate (ml/min) data for alprazolam

S. No	Flow Rate (ml/min)	System Suitability Results	
		USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	0.8	7063.3	1.3
2	1.0	6090.3	1.2
3	1.2	6998.0	1.3

Variation Of Mobile Phase Organic Composition:

(a) chromatogram showing less organic composition

(b) chromatogram showing more organic composition

Change in Organic Composition in the Mobile Phase for Sertaline HCL

S.No	Change in Organic Composition in the Mobile Phase	System Suitability Results	
		USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	10% less	4508.4	1.3
2	*Actual	4673.4	1.4
3	10% more	4318.1	1.3

Change in Organic Composition in the Mobile Phase for Alprazolam

S.No	Change in Organic Composition in the Mobile Phase	System Suitability Results	
		USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	10% less	6387.7	1.2
2	*Actual	6090.3	1.2
3	10% more	6232.5	1.2

Acceptance criteria:

Percentage RSD should be below 2.

- The %RSD obtained for change of flow rate, variation in mobile phase was found to be below 1, which is within the acceptance criteria. Hence the method is robust

CONCLUSION:

High performance liquid chromatography is at present one of the most sophisticated tool of the analysis. The estimation of Sertaline Hcl and Alprazolam was done by RP-HPLC. The Phosphate buffer was p^H 2.8 and the mobile phase was optimized with consists of Methanol: Phosphate buffer mixed in the ratio of 55:45 % v/ v. A C₁₈ column C18 (4.6 x 150mm, 5 μ m, Make: XTerra) or equivalent chemically bonded to porous silica particles was used as stationary phase. The detection was carried out using UV detector at 225 nm. The solutions were chromatographed at a constant flow rate of 1.0 ml/min. the linearity range of Sertaline Hcl and Alprazolam were found to be from 100-500 μ g/ml of Sertaline Hcl and 1-5 μ g/ml of Alprazolam. Linear regression coefficient was not more than 0.999.

The values of % RSD are less than 2% indicating accuracy and precision of the method. The percentage recovery varies from 98-102% of Sertaline Hcl and Alprazolam. LOD and LOQ were found to be within limit.

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